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The Academic Perspective:

A study of academic's perceptions of the importance of professional skills in engineering programmes in Ireland

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INTRODUCTION

It has been argued that Industry 4.0 will revolutionalise the way we live, work and communicate with each other and engineers must develop appropriate professional skills to meet the challenges associated with an ever-increasing, energy-consuming population [1,2]. Much has been written in the last ten years about the need for reform in engineering education and in particular the need to prepare graduates to work on a global scale in diverse teams [3,4,5,6]. Engineering education research has responded by informing innovative teaching pedagogies but there is limited research investigating the human influence on engineering education; the academic's perspective. This paper presents the results of an online survey of engineering academics in Ireland (n=273). The survey represents Phase 1 of a phenomenographic study to explore academic conceptions of the importance of professional skills in engineering programmes. Whilst the principal aim of the survey was to identify participants for Phase 2 interviews, we also sought to answer the following research question;

- What factors influence an academic's consideration of the relative importance of specific professional skills?

The outcomes highlight aspects of an academic's life experience which may have an influence on their views on the importance of professional skills. In order to reform engineering education, we must not only look at new policies and procedures, nor only consider innovative teaching pedagogies, we must also consider how we can encourage academics of all backgrounds to engage in educational reform. To do that we must better understand the beliefs, perceptions and conceptions of academics

working with students every day. The results of this survey provide an initial insight into the perceptions held by academic staff, which will be explored further in the main phenomenographic study.

1. BACKGROUND

Engineering has always been central to society's progress. In the past, the work of engineers significantly improved the quality of life of large populations through advances in technology and new innovations by improving healthcare, housing, nutrition, education, transport and communication. Today, engineers need skills and competencies to work in multi-disciplinary teams, transcending international boundaries and dealing with globally complex issues in unfamiliar surroundings. Policymakers, economists, politicians and social scientists will also be key members of any team which aims to provoke societal change. Engineering graduates need to be prepared to engage with a diverse range of people and disciplines outside of the technical domain of engineering itself.

1.1 Skills Requirements

There have been several calls for reform in engineering education, in order that graduates are equipped with the relevant skills to meet future societal challenges [3,4,5,6]. Engineering education researchers have informed innovative pedagogical practices which will help develop those skills in students.

The outcomes provide a rich catalogue for engineering educators, of initiatives which can be implemented in engineering programmes to meet this aim. There is no doubt that the use of project driven, group-based pedagogies, community-based projects, work placement and other student-centred approaches have a place in developing relevant professional skills. There is also an increasing recognition of the importance of emulating engineering practice in the classroom [5,7,8] which may suggest there is value in employing engineering academics who have engineering practice experience, sometimes called 'Pracademics'.

1.2 Career Academics versus Practical Experience

The academics involved in such innovative pedagogies do not need to be convinced about the benefits to the students of these teaching and learning methods, nor the importance of developing professional skills in students. However, not all engineering academics have the same interest in engineering education. Some may be less inclined to implement innovative pedagogies in the classroom or even move away from traditional didactic teaching where learning is predominantly seen as the accumulation of knowledge and technical skills. Other academics may consider that the development of professional skills is at the expense of technical knowledge, when in fact they can be developed in synergy.

Many engineering academics value research over teaching, which is encouraged by the research orientated promotional policies of many Institutions [5,9,10]. Pilcher et al., [11] argues that academics who have significant practice experience can be better placed to advise on the professional skills that engineers need in the workplace, and are in a position to teach using real-life examples. However, recruitment policies which require a PhD as a minimum qualification can create a barrier to those industry practitioners considering a mid-career change [11]. Pilcher et al., [11] also attest that it is questionable whether someone with industry experience would attain employment ahead of what is termed the 'career academic' in UK universities, as a result of the emphasis on research output metrics associated with the Research Excellence

Framework. The Royal Academy of Engineering (RAE) foresee perhaps the inevitable decline in industry experienced academic staff “HE appointments are often driven by a need to improve the research profile of an institution and many academics are recruited on their research track record. The result is that fewer lecturers in UK universities will have significant industrial experience.” [9,10, p.21]. Glenn Miller, Dean of Olin College, attests that many engineering academics are not trained to teach professional skills since they were hired for technical expertise and not their professional skills [6]. He proposes that teaching professional skills is more complex and nuanced than teaching technical skills which can easily be defined and measured. Whilst there are calls for the employment of more academic staff with industry experience [11], there is little published research on the variation of conceptions of ‘career academics’ and ‘industry experienced academics’.

The reform of engineering education can only be successful when academic staff come to understand the value of integrating professional skills within the curriculum. This survey comprises the first step to ascertain conceptions of what professional skills are and the value placed upon them by engineering academics.

2. SURVEY DESIGN

An online survey was circulated to all academics teaching on engineering programmes in Ireland. A response rate of 34% was achieved and n=273 (29%) respondents answered all questions. Whilst the main purpose of the survey was to identify interview participants and therefore a representative sample was not required, we were unable to determine if there was a biased response as overall population data of engineering academics in Ireland was unavailable. The survey collected information on the following topics; gender, age, HEI employer, engineering, other and teaching qualifications, membership of professional bodies, extent of academic experience, role and number of teaching hours, extent of industry experience, role, involvement with graduate recruitment or initial training of graduates.

Respondents were asked to score the importance of a list of professional skills for today’s engineering graduates. The list of skills was created from a systematic literature review of recent engineering educational publications and research papers and comprised 17 ‘non technical’ skills with just one ‘technical’ skill option. The purpose of the survey was to attempt to show some correlations and relationships between different aspects of the response data

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Demographics

The majority of respondents were male 72% (n= 197) and only 8% of respondents indicated an age below 35 years old. Approximately half (49%) of all respondents had achieved a PhD/EdD qualification. There was a wide range of primary qualification types selected by respondents with 87% (n=268) having an engineering qualification of some type. Respondents who answered ‘Other’ (n=39) indicated primary qualifications in the following broad categories; Science and Mathematics, Architecture and Construction, Business / MBA or Economics and Arts and Sociology. Sixty-nine respondents (23%) highlighted that they had undertaken an educational qualification, such as a CPD course, Post Graduate Certificate, Diploma or Masters in Education.

Eighty-two percent of respondents held roles in industry, with 34 academic staff still working or consulting in industry as shown in *Fig. 1*. The authors acknowledge

however that there may currently be academics working in joint research projects with industry in a consultancy role and whilst this may have prompted a 'yes' to this question, it is not the equivalent to spending several years in full-time practice. Thus, the responses from this category of academic must be considered carefully.

Those who had industry experience were asked to select the most senior role undertaken as indicated in *Fig. 2*. Intuitively, the number of respondents who undertook project management, people management and senior management roles increased with length of time spent in industry. However, even 46% of those with less than 5 years' industry experience had opportunities for people and project management roles suggesting that they would have had direct exposure to new graduates and hence an understanding of their attributes and potential weaknesses.

Fig. 1. No of respondents indicating length of industrial experience

Fig. 2. Percentage of respondents in each category indicating most senior role in industry

3.2 Importance of specific skills

Participants were asked to comment on the importance of a list of skills for the engineering graduates of today. A sliding scale question was used with 'Not important' (scored as 0) to 'Essential' (scored as 4). The authors acknowledge that a ranked question may have yielded a more robust response and the question was originally trialled in that fashion. Feedback from the pilot surveys indicated that a ranked question with 17 options did not flow well within the overall survey and respondents were more likely to drop out of the survey at that point. Hence respondents were asked to score each skill individually.

It is accepted that technical skills are a critical aspect of an engineer's formation, however, this question sought to investigate if respondents would choose 'excellent

technical skills' as more important than the other professional skills. Hence, the question was phrased "Assuming all engineering graduates have baseline technical skills, please indicate on a scale of 0-4, how important you think the following skills are for new engineering graduates of today?". A summary of the skills in rank order of importance calculated by mean score and the number of respondents which scored '0 -Not important' for specific skills are shown in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Average scoring of skills and number of respondents who indicated 'Not Important'

Professional Skill	Mean score (<i>M</i>) out of 4	No of resps who scored '0' - not important
Problem Solving (visualise and present practical solutions)	3.7 (<i>SD</i> = .48)	0
Communication (written, oral, listening skills)	3.6 (<i>SD</i> = .64)	0
Critical Thinking (evaluate all aspects of problems and solutions)	3.6 (<i>SD</i> = .65)	0
Practical Focus (apply theory to real life problems)	3.5 (<i>SD</i> = .60)	0
Self Direction (initiative, independent work, continuous learning)	3.5 (<i>SD</i> = .66)	0
Teamwork & Collaboration Skills (working with diverse people)	3.5 (<i>SD</i> = .71)	0
Character and Interpersonal Skills (integrity, social skills, ethic)	3.3 (<i>SD</i> = .78)	2
Excellence in Technical Skills (excellent technical capability)	3.2 (<i>SD</i> = .74)	0
Project Management (time management, planning skills)	3.1 (<i>SD</i> = .73)	0
Health & Safety (within a specific industry)	3.0 (<i>SD</i> = .95)	0
Research Skills (conduct research on a project or product)	2.9 (<i>SD</i> = .89)	3
Risk Management (identify and reduce risk)	2.7 (<i>SD</i> = .89)	2
Leadership (responsibility, leading and directing teams)	2.6 (<i>SD</i> = .86)	4
Global Outlook (international and intercultural skills)	2.5 (<i>SD</i> = .92)	4
Business Acumen (financial and budgeting /cost awareness)	2.3 (<i>SD</i> = .90)	8
General Knowledge (current affairs, politics)	2.0 (<i>SD</i> = .91)	12
Foreign Language Skills (communicate in a second language)	1.5 (<i>SD</i> = .96)	46

There is minimal difference in the scoring of the first six skills; Problem Solving, Communication, Critical Thinking, Practical Focus, Self Direction and Teamwork and Collaboration Skills, which are typical of those highlighted most often in the literature review exercise.

There is clearly a low score attributed to the importance of foreign language skills, which reflects the fact that English is the main form of communication in Ireland. The survey did not collect information relating to the language skills of the respondents, which would have provided further insight into the level of internationality in academic staff on engineering programmes in Ireland.

3.3 Gender differences

Initially, the results were sorted by gender and although this was not an initial research theme, it highlighted a surprising result. *Table 2* shows the average scores for females, males and those who chose 'Other or Prefer not to say'.

Table 2. Average scores of respondents on the importance of specific skills

	Female Mean Score (n=60)	Male Mean Score (n=197)	Other/Prefer not to say Mean Score (n=16)	Difference between Female - Male mean score
Problem Solving	3.78	3.71	3.81	0.08
Communication	3.71	3.59	3.44	0.12
Critical Thinking	3.78	3.53	3.56	0.26
Practical Focus	3.69	3.50	3.44	0.19
Self-Direction	3.62	3.44	3.50	0.17
Teamwork & Collaboration Skills	3.71	3.41	3.25	0.30*
Character and Interpersonal Skills	3.60	3.27	2.93	0.33*
Excellence in Technical Skills	3.17	3.23	3.00	-0.07*
Project Management	3.22	3.07	3.06	0.14
Health & Safety	3.20	2.94	3.31	0.26
Research Skills	3.12	2.82	2.94	0.31
Risk Management	2.97	2.66	2.75	0.31
Leadership	2.82	2.56	2.38	0.26
Global Outlook	2.80	2.46	2.50	0.34
Business Acumen	2.42	2.31	2.06	0.10
General Knowledge	2.15	2.01	1.88	0.15
Foreign Language Skills	1.58	1.43	1.38	0.16

*Indicates cases in which a statistically significant correlation was observed with regard to gender.

Within this survey, in all but one professional skill, women were more likely to score the importance of professional skills more highly than men, i.e., they appeared to place more importance on each skill than men did. Only 'Excellence in technical skills' was scored as less important by women than men. Since excellence in technical skills could be considered the only technical skill presented within the survey, and all others are non-technical, this suggests that within this population, female academics place more importance on non-technical skills in engineering graduates than male academics.

Although this initial result suggested a gendered difference, a statistical test carried out on SPSS sought to clarify which factor was the highest determinant of scoring of each professional skill; Age, Gender and Length of Industrial Experience. There were no correlations observed with regard to length of industry experience. A significant correlation was observed between Age and the importance of Teamwork and Collaboration Skills, Pearson's $r(238) = .127, p = .05$. The results also indicated that whilst there was no significant correlation observed between the overall average score and gender, significant correlations were identified between; Gender and the importance of Character and Interpersonal Skills, Pearson's $r(235) = .144, p = .03$, Teamwork and Collaboration, $r(238) = .128, p = .05$ and Excellence in Technical Skills, $r(237) = .145, p = .03$. As this finding was based on only one question within the survey, it is difficult to draw a solid conclusion however, it suggests that there is value in a further study to investigate differences in gender profiles of academic staff and their attitudes or approaches to teaching non-technical skills.

3.4 Influence of Industry Experience in relation to the importance of skills

Table 3 shows the percentage of respondents who selected 'Essential' for specific skills in relation to their industry experience. Fig. 3 also shows the average score for

specific skills in relation to industry experience. Industry experience has been refined to show comparisons between those with none or up to 5 years experience, and those with more than 6 years experience, but excluding those still working in industry, which has been discounted due to potential ambiguity in the question.

Table 3. Percentage of respondents selecting 'Essential' for specific skills

Industry Experience	Practical Focus	Leadership	Problem Solving
Greater than 6 years experience (n=110)	68.2%	19.1%	57.3%
Less than 6 years experience (n=135)	52.6%	13.3%	42.2%

Fig. 3. Mean score of respondents with differing industry experience on specific skills where 0 = 'Not important' and 4= 'Essential'

3.5 Skills and Industry Experience

The results suggest that the importance placed on practical focus, leadership skills and problem solving may be linked to time spent in industry and this is an issue we intend to address further within the main phenomenographic interview sessions. Problem Solving is clearly an essential requirement for engineers and achieved the highest score in the overall survey. It is also highlighted here as showing the largest difference in score between those with little or no industry experience and those with more than 5 years experience.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

The aim of this survey was to consider influences on an academic's opinion on the importance of specific professional skills in engineering graduates of today. The study showed that gender appears to have an influence not only on the importance of all professional skills, but particularly in relation to the importance of pure technical skills over non-technical skills. There is evidence to suggest that an academic's experience in industry also influences their judgements on the importance of professional skills and highlights the value of employing a diverse range of academic staff, including both career academics and those with industry experience, a proposal also put forward by Pilcher et al., [11].

The survey was administered to gather a range of views from academic staff in Ireland and to identify varied participants for a phenomenographic study. This work is ongoing. However, the results of the survey highlighted some interesting findings which will be investigated further in interviews. The authors would also welcome a comparative analysis of the same study of academics in another country.

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